

Gas Adsorption Method for Calculation of Pore-size Distribution in Solid Samples

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In this paper a modification over Pierce—circular method for calculation of pore-size distribution has been suggested. Pore volume and surface area values have been calculated by this modified method and the results have been compared with that of Pierce values. Our values have been found to be little higher than the Pierce values. This has been explained on the basis of wall film thickness which has been considered in our model.

In the field of catalysis and catalytic reactions, in addition to particle size and surface area, the elucidation of pore-size distribution^{1,2} has been responsible for much of the increased knowledge about catalytic activity. Although the true structure of pores involves a complicated geometry, but for calculation of pore-size distribution one generally assumes a model and on the basis of which the pore-size calculations are done. Usually pores are considered to be made up of cylinders or parallel plates but calculations based on cylindrical model⁷ give satisfactory results when compared with the experimental values.

In pore-size calculations, it has been shown by different workers that there will always be an adsorbed layer present on the wall of the capillaries when condensation takes place or an adsorbed layer will always be left over when desorption takes place. By using Kelvin equation³, one finds the value for the inner capillary radius, r_k for the condensed phase; but not for the adsorbed layer. The thickness of this adsorbed layer, therefore, must be taken into account in the calculation of pore-size distributions. The methods of Shull⁴, Oulton⁵, BJH⁶, Pierce⁷ and Wheeler⁸, have, of course, made a necessary correction for this adsorbed layer.

In our modified method an additional correction factor has been suggested for the pore-size distribution calculations. Previous workers considered that pores are made up of uniform cylinders. Further, they have assumed that at each step, the gas desorbed is composed of the gas evaporated from the meniscus or inner capillaries of the condensed phase, and the gas from the adsorbed film on the walls of the previously unfilled pores. But they did not take into account the decrement of the wall film thickness, though small, of those capillaries from which condensed liquid is going out. Hence a correction has been introduced for this loss also.

The total gas desorbed at a particular desorption

step can therefore be considered to be due to :

(a) The gas from the inner capillaries, i.e., from the condensed phase (Fig. 1.1)

Fig. 1. Physical Representation of Pore Conditions at Different Partial Pressures

(b) The gas from the adsorbed wall film of the previously emptied pores.

(c) The gas from the adsorbed wall film from which liquid is also evaporating.

Experimental

The usual BET volumetric gas adsorption-desorption apparatus was used for the determination of pore-size distribution in kaolinite and pyrophyllite clay samples, by using nitrogen gas as an adsorbate. These Indian clay samples were purchased from reputed commercial firms and were used as supplied (100-120 mesh). Prior to use, each sample was properly treated and evacuated for 5 to 6 hours in order to remove the adsorbed water and the adsorbed gases from the samples.

Results and Discussion

Method of Computation for Pore-size Distribution :

Let us assume that the pores are completely filled when the partial pressure, p_e/p_0 , is very close to 1. Now, when the partial pressure is allowed to drop slightly, the quantity of gas desorbed, V_1 , would be composed of the gas from the condensed phase of the inner capillaries V_{k_1} and the gas from the adsorbed layer (due to reduction of adsorbed layer thickness by t_1) of the same capillaries (Fig. 1.2) V_{i_1} . The contribution from other capillaries would be zero as they are completely filled at first desorption step. Therefore, the experimental volume desorbed at the first reduction of the partial pressure from its saturation value, would be

$$V_1 = V_{k_1} + V_{i_1} \quad \dots (1)$$

$$\text{or } V_1 = V_{k_1} + t_1 \times S_1 \quad \dots (2)$$

where, S_1 stands for inner surface area exposed due to evaporation of V_{k_1} , and t_1 is the diminution in the wall film thickness of the adsorbed layer (Fig. 1.2), S_1 can also be represented in terms of V_{k_1} as

$$S_1 = \frac{2V_{k_1}^*}{\bar{r}_{k_1}} \quad \dots (3)$$

where, \bar{r}_{k_1} is the mean Kelvin radius for the pressure range over which a decrement of gas has taken place. Substitution of equation (3) in (2) gives

$$V_{k_1} = V_1 \left(\frac{\bar{r}_{k_1}}{\bar{r}_{k_1} + t_1} \right) \quad \dots (4)$$

The corresponding area exposed due to desorption of V_1 (i.e., due to evaporation of V_{k_1} and evaporation of adsorbed layer) is given by

$$S_1 = \left(\frac{2V_1^*}{\bar{r}_{k_1} + t_1} \right) \quad \dots (5)$$

* $S_1 = 2\pi\bar{r}_{k_1} L$; $V_{k_1} = \pi\bar{r}_{k_1}^2 L$

** $S_1 = \pi 2(\bar{r}_{k_1} + t_1)L$; $V_1 = \pi(\bar{r}_{k_1} + t_1)^2 L$.

Now for the second desorption step, the volume V_2 , which goes out, would be composed of the gas from the inner capillaries V_{k_2} (Fig. 1.3), the gas from adsorbed layer of the same capillaries, V_{i_2} and the gas from the adsorbed layer of the previously emptied pore, V_{r_2} , which occurred in the first desorption step.

$$\text{Hence, } V_2 = V_{k_2} + V_{i_2} + V_{r_2} \quad \dots (6)$$

The above equation can also be written as

$$V_2 = V_{k_2} + t_2 \times S_2' + t_2 \times S_1 \quad \dots (7)$$

where, S_1 represents the surface area of all the previously emptied pores, and t_2 is the decrease in the adsorbed layer in the second desorption step. Now S_2' can be represented, similar to equation (3), as

$$S_2' = \frac{2V_{k_2}}{\bar{r}_{k_2}} \quad \dots (8)$$

Substitution of equation (8) in (7) gives

$$V_{k_2} = (V_2 - t_2 \times S_1) \frac{\bar{r}_{k_2}}{\bar{r}_{k_2} + 2t_2} \quad \dots (9)$$

Similarly, for the next desorption step, the amount of the gas evaporated from the inner capillaries, i.e., from the condensed phase, is given by

$$V_{k_3} = V_3 - t_3(S_2 + S_1) \frac{\bar{r}_{k_3}}{\bar{r}_{k_3} + 2t_3} \quad \dots (10)$$

or, in general, it can be written as

$$V_k = V - t \times \Sigma(S) \frac{\bar{r}_k}{\bar{r}_k + 2t} \quad \dots (11)$$

V_k is the volume of the inner cylinder. The actual pore volume, V_p is related to V_k by the expression :

$$V_p = V_k \left(\frac{\bar{r}_p}{\bar{r}_k} \right)^2 \quad \dots (12)$$

\bar{r}_p is the mean pore radius for the pressure range over which gas is desorbed.

\bar{r}_p is related to \bar{r}_k and t by the expression,

$$\bar{r}_p = \bar{r}_k + t$$

where, t is the wall thickness. The value of t is calculated by using the Wheeler⁹ equation

$$t = 4.3 \left[\frac{5}{2.303 \log p_0/p_e} \right]^{1/3}$$

where, p_e is the equilibrium pressure.

The calculation of the area of the pore walls S_1 , corresponding to the decremental volumes, V_1 is based on equation (5) which for small decrements may be rewritten in terms of V_{k_1} , by using equation (4) as

$$S_1 = \frac{2(\bar{r}_{k_1} + 2t_1)}{\bar{r}_{k_1}(\bar{r}_{k_1} + t_1)} \times V_{k_1} \quad \dots \quad (13)$$

All calculations for pore volumes and surface areas for the samples were carried out by computer programming.

The values of V_p and S were obtained by adding all the V_p values and S values of each desorption step, calculated from equations (12) and (13). These values have been shown in Table 1.

These values were calculated by using (1) Pierce Circular Model⁷ and (2) ours Modified Model (as already described earlier). On comparing the results, it can be concluded that the cumulative pore volume and the cumulative surface area calculated by the modified method for the kaolinite and pyrophyllite clay samples are little higher than the values obtained by Pierce circular model. This little higher values of ours are due to taking into consideration the wall film thickness which is going out simultaneously with the condensed liquid from the same pore.

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TABLE 1—COMPARISON OF CUMULATIVE PORE VOLUME AND CUMULATIVE SURFACE AREA OF SELECTED INDIAN CLAY SAMPLES DETERMINED BY 'PIERCE CIRCULAR MODEL' AND OURS 'MODIFIED MODEL'

Clay Mineral Type	Circular Model (Pierce)		Modified Model	
	Cumulative Pore volume (V_p) (cc-STPg ⁻¹)	Cumulative Surface area (S) (m ² g ⁻¹)	Cumulative Pore volume (V_p) (cc-STPg ⁻¹)	Cumulative Surface area (S) (m ² g ⁻¹)
Kaolinite	0.008	6.86	0.012	6.90
Pyrophyllite	0.039	30.10	0.050	31.00

Table 1 represents the results of cumulative pore volume, $\Sigma(V_p)$, and the cumulative surface area, $\Sigma(S)$ for kaolinite and pyrophyllite clay samples.

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